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Desalinization of degraded soils by atmospheric precipitation and Biosolvent for saving water resources

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Abstract. In the Syrdarya region of Uzbekistan, the influence of atmospheric precipitation on changes in the degree of salinity and chemical composition of the upper 30 cm soil layer was studied. Experiment options: 1 - loosening the soil to a depth of 70 cm, 2 - loosening, followed by soil treatment with preparation containing polymaleic acid. A decrease in the degree of soil salinity by 7 - 8 dS/m has been established with the help of only 302 mm of precipitation, without water wasted for leaching. The decrease in soil salinity was: according to EU, 56% - in option 2, and 52% - in option 1. According to TDS, the salinity reduction was: - 61 and 52%, according to SO⁴ - 58 and 47%. The content of calcium in the variant with the use of Biosolvent decreased by 48%, and in the control variant, it increased by 15%. It has been estimated that with a decrease in salinity from 16 to 8 dS/m, a possible increase in the yield of a salt-tolerant barley crop by 1.6 t/ha is possible. Taking into account the costs of loosening and tillage with the preparation, the net income of the farmer can be \$480/ha.

1. Introduction

According to the regional service of reclamation control of the Ministry of Water Resources of Uzbekistan, saline irrigated soils in the Syrdarya region, in eastern Uzbekistan occupy 97% of the territory, including soils with a low degree of salinity make up 71%, moderately saline soils - 22%, and highly saline soils - 3%. In Mirzaabad district, 100% of the area of irrigated lands is saline. At the same time, slightly saline soils occupy 57% of the irrigated ones, moderately saline soils - 51%, and 12% are occupied by soils with a high degree of salinity. Salinization worsens the physical and chemical properties of soils, reduces the effectiveness of mineral fertilizers, and inhibits cultivated plants (Data from the Ministry of Water Resources of the Republic of Uzbekistan). «The development of unsustainable irrigation schemes in the region Mirzachul has had significant environmental and ecological impacts associated with elevated water tables; the abandonment of large tracks of land due to salinization; declining crop productivity and returns on investments; enhanced salinity levels in irrigation return flows to the two dominant rivers that has had a profound effect on aquatic species and quality of water. The dominant approach adopted by irrigation farmers to mitigate salinity in the region is to apply excessive amounts of water to salt affected fields in order to leach salts below the effective root zone. It has been estimated that between 20 – 25% of the annual available surface water in the region is used for leaching. The application of additional surface waters to fields has resulted in the

development of elevated water tables that effectively exacerbates the problem through the mobilization of further salt. The studies clearly showed the areas with the vegetation improvement and continuous degradation».

The major challenge of land reclamation in a significant part of the district is the on-going deterioration of the irrigation and drainage networks. At the expense of long periods of un-use of lands for irrigated agriculture, many current areas of abandoned low-productive degraded lands were formed within the contours of irrigated lands.

Therefore, soil salinization is a extremely urgent challenge and example of a wide-spread environmental hazard that limits exploiting the agricultural potential and threatens food and livelihood security of the rural and urban populations in the country and is closely caused by the current poor agricultural management practices in combination with an overexploitation of the water resources, especially in the arid climates [1].

In the territories of the lands of the Hungry Steppe during the periods of wide-scale development, e.g. from the middle to the end of the 20th century, during which irrigation and drainage infrastructures were built, there currently are abandoned pieces of lands throughout the region. This is caused because the soils most often have developed unfavorable properties, e.g they have become saline and compact, due to the presence of interlayers with a high content (up to 50%) of gypsum and carbonates. Since the water resources of Uzbekistan are mainly provided from the transboundary rivers the Syrdarya and Amudarya, and virtually 90 percent are used in the agricultural sector for irrigated agriculture. Uzbekistan has its own water resources, which are less than 20% of those required for use [2]. Water resources are limited by limits, detailed in interstate agreements, and depend on the water content of both rivers. Periodically the shortage of water resources will obviously deepen due to climate change.

Despite the high water cuse for flushing saline lands, during the development process (up to 20 thousand m³/ha or more), by now virtually all land has become saline and degraded. Nevertheless, they are valuable for agricultural production still, and, both in the present and future, these lands are worth restoring and maintained for further use, also due to rapid population growth the concurrent need to ensure long-term food security of the republic. This is a challenging task, the solution of which requires to technical feasible and financial viable solutions thus, considering also the costs of water resources, and look into new approaches, technologies and solutions. The lack of water for irrigation in Uzbekistan requires a very careful attention to the cost of water in all sectors of the economy and especially in agriculture, including land reclamation. In recent publications, conducted on the territory of the Syrdarya region, by using e.g. remote methods [3], a clear description of the situation in this region is given. Here it is noted”n recent years, degradation of the drainage networks and progressive water insufficiency combined with uncertainty of the water supply related to the global climate change aggravated the situation with land degradation. Obviously, a revitalization of the drainage networks is expensive and under conditions of insufficiency of water and concurrently challenged by a growing uncertainty of the impact of climate change, combatting measures may be only partially effective. Moreover, economic difficulties require inexpensive, but cost- and time-effective approaches that could be adopted by the farmers”.

According to the theory of regulation of the soil salt regime, a fundamental concept is the reducing soil salinity during the growing season, for a specific crop, according to the principle of leaching irrigation regime (LR-leaching requirement LF - leaching fraction), taking into account the salinity used for irrigation water [7]. At the same time, drainage must be necessarily provided [4-8]. In the same sources, for successful washing of the soil from salts, the value of the rate of water infiltration into the soil is important to consider, which should not be too low but neither be too high. The leaching irrigation regime is inevitably created during furrow irrigation, due to water infiltration, planning the leaching irrigation regime in the conditions of Uzbekistan, with mass irrigation of crops during the growing season and with a shortage of water, is impossible.

In a review of the literature on reducing the negative impact of soil salinity on crop yields [1], a global meta-analysis of 128 paired observations of soil quality and yield from 30 studies was conducted. The authors of the study compared the performance of various Soil Improvement Crops (SICS) systems

to combat soil salinity in 11 countries to identify the most promising. The analysis showed that, in addition to optimizing irrigation and drainage management on a case-by-case basis, a combination of soil fertilizers, conditioners and crop residue management (conservation agriculture) can contribute to a significant reduction in soil salinity and a significant increase in crop yields. Also, the possibility of washing the soil with precipitation [8, 9] and the feasibility of special soil loosening to enhance infiltration are underlined. Previous studies [6, 7] mention the use of sulfuric acid as a chemical ameliorant of alkaline and gypsum soils by adding it to the water or the soil. The authors also note that soil salinization is closely related also to the use of inefficient farming system practices (i.e. crop selection, crop rotation, tillage practices, irrigation, and application of nutrients as well as pest control in a specific field over a given period). To make farming systems both more sustainable and profitable, it is imperative to improve soils, which means it is necessary to break the negative spiral of degradation, increased costs, and environmental damage [1]. Among the possible ways of using the degraded, previously developed lands of the Hungry Steppe, due to the failure of reclamation measures and the persistently low productivity of lands, it was proposed to use the territory of this zone for livestock breeding purposes [10]. On the possibility of soil desalination with the help of autumn-winter precipitation, if deep loosening of the soils of saline areas is done in autumn. The efficiency of desalination of cultivated highly saline soils of autumn-winter precipitation against the background of deep loosening of the soil was studied by Turabekov in the Jizzakh steppe and results were obtained that allow saving a certain amount of water [11].

Published works indicate that the movement of salts by raindrops is more environmentally friendly and efficient than washing the soil with a layer of water using special checks [9].

Reducing the cost of water for leaching saline lands can be achieved also by the amplification of salt leaching when using so-called conditioners, e.g. through the preparation of soil ameliorants. An international practice to combat saline soils e.g., salt correctors are recommended, e.g. preparations

In a previous study by the authors in 2020 in the Khavast district of the Syrdarya region, it was found that a deep loosening of the soil combined with the Biosolvent preparation ensured the desalination of the upper 30 cm soil layer with precipitation (300 mm) by 4-5 dS / m, which is adequate to flushing by checks with a layer water 20 cm [20]. The purpose of this study is to clarify the possibility and effectiveness of reducing the salinity of degraded abandoned lands, due to winter-spring precipitation, with deep loosening of compacted soil and its treatment with a preparation with polymaleic acid, such as Sper Sal 35, Spersal R SL, DeSaltus [12-15].

To carry out field work on the abandoned lands of the Mirzaabad district in the winter-spring period of 2021-2022, a site was selected and a special experiment was carried out.

The object of research therefore is to develop efficient counter measures for combatting saline and compacted lands on the territory of the so-called Hungry Steppe. The use of Biosolvent during leaching, with its dilution 1:10 and tillage inside the checks, before pouring water, showed an increase in the leaching of harmful ions by 35...42% and the possibility of saving water more 2000 m³/ha. The use of the drug during the growing season, by spraying the top of the furrows before irrigation, provided an increase in the leaching of salts from a layer of 0-70 cm by 18-25% and an increase in the cotton yield of more than 7 centners per hectare, due to a decrease in osmotic pressure in the soil without additional water consumption [16-19].

2. Materials and methods

To reach the objectives, Experiments were carried out in the Mirzaabad district of the Syrdarya region of Uzbekistan on a territory, which were previously developed in the 60-70s of the 20th century. The locally produced soil improver Biosolvent (an analogue of the foreign preparation Spersal), also containing polymaleic acid, was tested as an enhancer of salt leaching from the soils of the Hungry Steppe during leaching and irrigation. previous studies [e.g. 16-19] the showed the impact of Biosolvent according to fixed scheme: laboratory columns -> vegetative vessels - >farmer's field. This approach made it possible to capture in more detail the qualitative and quantitative impact of the drug on soils and to develop a technology for its practical application. As a result, the norms of the drug were established

when using it during the period of leaching the soil with a layer of water according by checks, quantitative indicators of the effect of the drug on the intensity of salt leaching were revealed, and changes in the chemical composition in the soils of the Syrdarya region.

The experiment was carried out on an area of 2.24 hectares in two options: 1. "Control" – which consist of the usual loosening of the soil to a depth of 70 cm; 2. "treatment" - loosening and a subsequent spraying of the soil with a preparation Biosolvent, which enhances the leaching of salts in dilution with water 1:10, at the cost of the drug - 10 l/ha. Soil salinity control was carried out by taking and analyzing the chemical composition of soil samples, performed by water extraction for the period December 2021 and April 2022. Soil samples were taken along the horizons of 0-30 and 30-70 cm, at five points located using the "envelope" method in each of the options. The effectiveness of soil desalinization in the experimental variants was revealed by comparing the analysis data for December and April. The amount of atmospheric precipitation for the indicated period was 302 mm, which corresponds to the leaching rate of 2500 m³/ha.

In the samples taken by genetic horizons from a soil section with a depth of more than 1.25 m, the soil properties of the site were determined (General accepted methodology in soil science).

According to the mechanical composition, the soil is homogeneous, with a predominance of the dust fraction and is assessed according to the FAO classification [7] as Silty Loam. The soil profile is compacted in the upper half meter, up to 1.77 t/m³, below 1.47-1.57 g/cm³, along the entire profile up to 1.0 meters almost evenly contains about 18-20% calcium carbonate Ca(CO₃)₂, (table 1).

Table 1. Soil characteristics of the study area.

Genetic horizon, cm	Bulk density, t/m	Sand, 0.05-2.0	Dust, 0.002-0.05	Clay <0.002	FAO classification	pH	CaCO ₃ %	
0-22	1.78	29	56	16	ZL	Silty Loam	8.5	20.2
22-51	1.76	30	55	15	ZL	Silty Loam	8.5	19.7
51-71	1.57	35	55	10	ZL	Silty Loam	8.5	19.3
71-100	1.47	40	51	8	ZL	Silty Loam	8.3	18.0
100-125	1.51	48	43	10	L	Loam	8.3	17.6
>125-	1.54	51	39	10	L	Loam	8.3	16.8

Water infiltration is less than 0.01 m/day; the groundwater level was at 1.7 m; the mineralization of ground water > 10 g/l.

The water diverting drainage on the site was working unsatisfactorily and required to be cleaned, while a field drainage was absent. The irrigation network is represented by a concrete flume channel. The initial soil salinity varied from 11.0 to 16.6 dS/m, in the 0-30 cm layer and from 6.7-13.9 dS/m in the 70 cm layer. According to the EC_e of the upper soil layer the soils are highly saline., and the data were compared by observation periods in the experimental variants. To compare both treatments, data were used of points located in places of high-quality loosening of the soil. The results of the analyzes were processed statistically and graphically in the Excel program.

3. Results and discussion

After independence from the former Soviet Union in 1991, Uzbekistan initiated several reforms including market liberalization, land privatization and the introduction of participatory approaches to water distribution. Irrigated agriculture plays a dominant role in the economy of Uzbekistan in general and in the study region "Hungry Steppe" in particular. Both on national and regional levels, more than 90% of all water resources are used by the agricultural sector [21, 22]. Starting in 1960s, a vast irrigation

network was constructed in the Syrdarya region to service croplands. However, irrigation network efficiency does not exceed 60% [23, 24].

The 302 mm precipitation that fell between December to April 2021-2022 changed the content of salts and ions in the 0-30 cm soil layer at all observation points, (figure 1). At the beginning of observations (December 2021), some differences in soil salinity indicators such as e.g. existed, but there were no significant differences anymore between individual points of the treatments (figure 1). In contrast, in April 2022, there are noticeable differences in the content of salts and ions between the individual points of each of the treatments. most likely because soil loosening in the control part of experimental area was carried out unevenly, caused by the wide distance between the teeth of the ripper compared to the treatment.

More significant changes submerged in the salt contents between December and April at several observation points such as O3, O5 and K2, K3, K5 in all cases the soil here was well loosened), and where the leaching values are less, observation points O2, O4 and K1, K4 - the soil is insufficiently loosened.

The study confirmed that against the background of deep loosening and spraying with Biosolvent, atmospheric precipitation (302 mm) can desalinate the topsoil up to 5 dS/m, creating conditions for sowing seeds of crops, the irrigation of which will continue the process of salt leaching. The use of atmospheric precipitation for soil desalination allows saving irrigation water and gradually restoring abandoned lands for salt-tolerant, industrial or fodder crops.

Table 2. Comparison of leaching of salts and ions from the soil layer of 0-30 cm by precipitation in the Mirzaabad district of the Syrdarya region.

Indicators		treatment (E)		Control (C)			Average by points of effective leaching of salts		
		Code of observation point		3 K	5 K	(E)	(C)	Diff. (E-C)	
		3 O	5 O						2 K
pH	Dec.21	8.6	8.5	8.7	8.6	8.7	8.63	8.64	-0.01
	Apr.22	8.8	8.4	8.3	8.3	8.2	8.57	8.38	0.19
	Diff.	0.2	-0.2	-0.4	-0.3	-0.5	0	-0.4	0.4
	%	2.1	-2.2	-4.3	-3.4	-5.2	-0.1	-4.3	4.2
ECe, dS/m	Dec.21	11.0	12.8	16.6	14.0	16.5	11.9	15.7	-3.8
	Apr.22	4.6	5.9	8.0	6.0	8.8	5.3	7.6	-2.4
	Diff.	-6.4	-7.0	-8.6	-8.0	-7.7	-6.7	-8.1	1.4
	%	-57.8	-54.2	-51.7	-56.9	-46.7	-56.0	-51.8	-4.3
TDS, %	Dec.21	1.22	1.37	1.75	1.62	1.78	1.30	1.72	-0.42
	Apr.22	0.43	0.58	0.95	0.64	0.90	0.51	0.83	-0.32
	Diff.	-0.79	-0.79	-0.80	-0.99	-0.88	-0.79	-0.89	0.10
	%	-64.6	-57.5	-45.7	-60.8	-49.6	-61.1	-52.0	-9.0
Cl', %	Dec.21	0.11	0.15	0.25	0.09	0.19	0.13	0.18	-0.05
	Apr.22	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.04	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.00
	Diff.	-0.08	-0.13	-0.21	-0.06	-0.17	-0.10	-0.15	0.04
	%	-73.3	-84.1	-84.3	-61.5	-90.7	-78.7	-78.9	0.2
SO ⁴ %	Dec.21	0.65	0.72	0.86	0.96	0.96	0.69	0.93	-0.24
	Apr.22	0.24	0.34	0.56	0.34	0.56	0.29	0.49	-0.20
	Diff.	-0.41	-0.38	-0.30	-0.62	-0.40	-0.40	-0.44	0.04
	%	-63.7	-52.8	-35.1	-64.6	-41.9	-58.2	-47.2	-11.0
Ca ²⁺ %	Dec.21	0.11	0.13	0.13	0.15	0.15	0.12	0.14	-0.02
	Apr.22	0.05	0.08	0.14	0.18	0.18	0.06	0.17	-0.10
	Diff.	-0.06	-0.05	0.01	0.03	0.03	-0.06	0.02	
	%	-55.6	-40.3	9.1	20.0	18.4	-47.9	15.8	
Mg ²⁺ %	Dec.21	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.06	0.05	0.06	0.06	0.00
	Apr.22	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.00
	Diff.	-0.03	-0.04	-0.05	-0.04	-0.03	-0.04	-0.04	0
	%	-64.4	-59.4	-62.0	-69.5	-54.7	-61.9	-62.1	0.2

Figure 1. Salt and mineral leaching caused by precipitation in the 0-30 cm soil layer.

An economic assessment of the proposed technology was made on the example of a salt-tolerant crop - barley, the salt tolerance threshold of which, providing a 100% yield - 4 t/ha, is 8 dS/m. According to this experience, without the cost of water and labor for washing, loosening the soil using Biosolvent, desalination with winter precipitation, makes it possible to obtain a decrease in soil salinity in the 0-30 cm layer from 16.0 to 8 dS/m (see table 2).

Soil salinity in E_{ce} decreased from 11.9 to 5.3 dS/m (difference of 6.6 dS/m), - in the Experimental option and from 15.7 to 7.6 dS/m (difference of 8.1 dS/m), - in the control. In both options, the soils moved from the category of highly saline (according to FAO) to the category of medium degree of salinity. The decrease in soil salinity according to E_{ce} , expressed as a percentage of the initial value, respectively, amounted to: 56.0% in the Experiment variant and 51.8% in the "control".

Leaching of salts from soils with a higher degree of salinity usually occurs more intensively: the same volume of water carries out more salts. Factor, higher initial soil salinity in the control, and this complicated the assessment of the effectiveness of Biosolvent. Nevertheless, its influence on the leaching process is still revealed.

The decrease in salinity, expressed as a percentage of the initial values, in the treatment was 61.1 % as in contrast to the Control (of 52%) in terms of the total salt content (TDS): hence a difference of 9.0%), yet, for chloride in both options this was 79%, and for magnesium - about 62%, for SO_4^{2-} - 58.2 and 47.2% (or a difference of 11.0%). The greatest difference between the variants was seen in the change of in the calcium ion content: in the treatment with Biosolvent, this was washed out from the upper layer by -47.9%, but in the control variant, its content increased even by 15.8%. The release (dissolution) of calcium can mean an improvement in the chemical composition of the soil absorption complex, a decrease in the content of calcium carbonate. More deeply these processes should be clarified by further research. Figure 2 shows the change in the calcium content in the soil profile under the influence of precipitation and Biosolvent.

Figure 2. The effect of the Biosolvent on calcium leaching by sediments (left – Option, right - Control).

From the point of view of chemical processes, a more intensive decrease in the calcium content of the soil with the use of Biosolvent can be explained by the fact that preparations containing polymaleic acid increase solubility and ensures the release of calcium in the soil solution.

«SperSal 35 increases the solubility of calcium so that it becomes incorporated into the soil more easily, increasing aggregate size and improving overall soil structure. This increase in soil porosity leads to improved water infiltration rates for a healthier, more functional soil profile» [12]. In addition, this preparation interacts with clay suspension, forming large and stable aggregates, which allows faster washing out of salts from the root zone. Spersal also conditions the soil and improves the movement of water and nutrients, interrupting the crystallization of calcium carbonate [15].

According to [25, 26], barley yield losses are 5% per 1 dS/m of soil salinity. With soil salinity of 16 dS/m, it was possible to obtain a barley yield 1.6 t/ha less: $4 - (16-8) \cdot 0.05 \cdot 4 = 2.4$ t/ha. With the cost of

selling barley \$ 400 Usd. per ton, the cost of additional production will be: $1.6 * 400 = \$ 640$ Usd. If the farmer's expenses for loosening, purchasing Biosolvent and spraying the soil are subtracted from this amount (which, respectively, are: $\$70 + \$70 + \$20 = \160), then the farmer's net income will be: $\$640 - \$160 = \$480$ Usd.

4. Conclusions

The study confirmed that under the conditions of the Mirzaabad district of the Syrdarya region of Uzbekistan, against the background of deep loosening of the soil and spraying with Biosolvent, atmospheric precipitation (302 mm) can desalinate the top 30 cm soil layer up to 5 dS / m, creating conditions for sowing seeds of crops, irrigation which will continue the process of salt leaching.

The use of Biosolvent enhances the leaching of part of the total amount of salts and sulfates. The main effect is to increase the leaching of calcium. For carbonate soils, this is important, since repeated soil treatment with the preparation is likely to gradually destroy carbonates and improve soil properties.

The technology of using atmospheric precipitation for soil desalination, only with the help of loosening, the use of the Biosolvent preparation and atmospheric precipitation (without soil leaching) allows saving irrigation water and gradually restoring abandoned lands for salt-tolerant, technical or forage crops.

An economic calculation performed on the example of sowing barley with a salt tolerance of 8 dS/m showed that with this method of desalination of highly saline (16 dS/m) soils, a farmer's net income can be \$480.

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